

Diazoketiminato complexes of d^8 -triad : A comparative study on molecular and electronic structure, electronic spectra and electron transfer properties

Jahar Lal Pratihar

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal, India

E-mail : jlpr@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 06 July 2009, revised 06 July 2010, accepted 20 July 2010

Abstract : Reaction of 2-(arylo)aniline, H_2L , **1**, [where H_2L is 2-(ArN=N)C₆H₄-NH₂; Ar = C₆H₅ (for H_2L^1), *p*-MeC₆H₄ (for H_2L^2), H represents the amino protons], with Na₂PdCl₄ or K₂PtCl₄ or Ni(OAc)₂·4H₂O afford green bis chelates of composition (HL)₂M (M = Ni or Pd or Pt), **2**. Only the synthesis and molecular structure of (HL)₂Ni has been determined. The formation of six membered diazoketiminato chelate of bidentate (N, N) anionic ligand HL⁻ has been determined by spectroscopic and X-ray studies. This structural feature has been attributed to the delocalization of negative charge of the anionic ligand precursor H_2L due to the dissociation of an amino proton. The serial redox responses of (HL)₂M complexes have been observed in their cyclic voltammograms. The composition of frontier orbital of the diazoketiminato complexes were evaluated by EHMO method. The redox orbital were identified on matching the electrochemical results with the semiempirical electronic structure of the complexes.

Keywords : d^8 -Triad, diazoketiminato chelates, redox, EHMO.

Introduction

Transition metal chelates incorporating azo ligands have drawn much attention during the last few decades¹⁻²⁵ due to their several interesting characteristics such as coordination modes^{1-7,11-22}, molecular geometry^{1-7,11-15,18-22}, C-H bond activation^{1,2,7,14-17}, catalytic activity, photophysical⁸⁻¹⁰, photochemical^{23,24}, liquid crystals and electron transfer properties¹¹⁻²⁵. We reported the preparation and properties of platinum metal chelates incorporating deprotonated 2-(arylo)aniline, H_2L , ligands where the anionic ligands bind in bidentate fashion with delocalization within the ligand backbone. The structural aspects of diazoketiminato complexes of Pd^{II}, Pt^{II} and Au^{III} have been addressed considering the delocalization within the ligand frame work as the key factor³⁻⁶.

Herein, the reaction of 2-(arylo)aniline with nickel acetate and formation of diazoketiminato chelate of Ni^{II} has been described. The complex formations have been authenticated on the basis of X-ray structural data and ¹H NMR studies. A comparative study of Pd^{II}, Pt^{II} and Ni^{II} diazoketiminato complexes on the basis of structural and spectral characterization have been studied. The electron transfer properties of the diazoketiminato complexes

(HL)₂M have been examined electrochemically and results were correlated with the EHMO results.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of (HL)₂Ni has been standardized and carried out in our laboratory. The reaction of 2-(arylo)aniline³⁻⁵, H_2L , **1**, with Ni(OAc)₂·4H₂O was carried out in 2 : 1 mole ratio in refluxing methanol and in presence of K₂CO₃. The green complex of composition (HL)₂Ni, **2a**, was isolated there from in good yield. It is worth mentioning that the base K₂CO₃ was not

M = Ni (**2a**), Pd (**2b**), Pt (**2c**)

R = H for H_2L^1 , Me for H_2L^2

necessary to be used for the preparation of diazoketiminato complexes of heavier congeners (Pd or Pt) or Group-10 metals with H_2L due to spontaneous deprotonation of amino function during the reaction. Therefore dissociation of amino proton of H_2L has been realized to be an essential criterion towards the formation of diazoketiminato chelates of transition metal ions.

The diamagnetic green bis complex $(HL)_2Ni$ displayed characteristic UV-Vis spectrum as shown in Fig. 1 for $(HL^1)Ni$ is as representative, spectral data are collected

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectrum of $(HL^1)_2Ni$.

in Experimental section. The low energy absorption near at 651 nm comparable to $(HL^1)_2Pd$ and $(HL^1)_2Pt$ (at 630 nm and 756 nm respectively) has been assigned to charge transfer transition from metal-ligand mixed HOMO to ligand LUMO (EHMO result see below).

In IR spectrum of $(HL)_2Ni$ a sharp single band at 3322 cm^{-1} appears as in $(HL)_2Pd$ and $(HL)_2Pt$ which is characteristic of ν_{NH} , this indicates the deprotonation of amino group³⁻⁵. The $\nu_{N=N}$ of $(HL)_2Ni$ appeared at 1382 cm^{-1} in contrast to that of the $\nu_{N=N}$ of ligand H_2L near 1460 cm^{-1} signifying the coordination of azo nitrogen³⁻⁵. A new band, near $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, in the IR spectra of the complexes unlike the ligand, has been attributed to imine formation.

The 1H NMR spectrum of $(HL)_2Ni$ exhibited a singlet at $\delta 5.82$ and 5.89 for $(HL^1)_2Ni$ and $(HL^2)_2Ni$ respectively, equivalent to one amino proton per ligand, confirming the binding of deprotonated form of the ligands (HL^-) similar to $(HL)_2Pd$ and $(HL)_2Pt$. The upfield shift of aromatic protons for $(HL)_2M$ ($\delta 7.47$ to 5.93) compared to the corresponding ligands ($\delta 7.80$ to 6.75) is a general feature in the 1H NMR spectra. This observation is consistent with the coordination of anionic ligands³⁻⁵. The aromatic region of 1H NMR spectrum of $(HL^1)_2Ni$ is

complicated due overlapping signals whereas the spectrum of $(HL^2)_2Ni$ resolved well to infer the structure in solution. Two triplets for (C9 and C10) and two doublets were appearing at $\delta 6.80$, 6.36 and $\delta 7.29$, 6.02 . Other two doublets, each of two equivalent protons, for (C2, C6 and C3, C5) appear at $\delta 7.74$ and 7.18 . Data are given in Experimental section.

X-Ray crystal structure :

Suitable crystals of $(HL^1)_2Ni$, for X-ray studies, were grown upon slow evaporation of dichloromethane solution. A perspective view of the molecular structure (X-ray) has been shown in Fig. 2. Selected bond distances and angles are collected in Table 1. Each of the

Fig. 2. Molecular structure of $(HL^1)_2Ni$ with atom numbering scheme. The hydrogen atoms excepting on N(3) of the amino groups have been omitted for clarity.

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) for compound $(HL^1)_2Ni$

Bond distances			
Ni(1)-N(1)	1.883(4)	C(7)-C(12)	1.417(4)
Ni(1)-N(3)	1.821(3)	C(12)-C(11)	1.413(4)
N(1)-N(2)	1.294(4)	C(10)-C(11)	1.347(5)
N(2)-C(7)	1.341(3)	C(9)-C(10)	1.395(5)
N(1)-C(1)	1.437(4)	C(8)-C(9)	1.334(4)
N(3)-C(12)	1.322(4)	C(7)-C(8)	1.415(4)
Bond angles			
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(3)	88.28(9)	Ni(1)-N(3)-C(12)	128.96(16)
C(7)-N(2)-N(1)	120.43(18)	N(2)-C(7)-C(12)	124.09(18)
N(3)-C(12)-C(7)	120.98(19)	Ni(1)-N(1)-N(2)	129.87(14)

deprotonated ligand binds the metal in a bidentate (N, N) fashion one ligand is symmetry equivalent to the other, held in a *trans* position. The MN₄ coordination sphere is planar, consistent with the square planar geometry of bivalent metal and uni-negative anionic ligand (HL)⁻. The chelate ring is, however, not planar. The fragment containing N2, C7, C8, C9, C10, C11 and C12 is satisfactorily planar. The N3-C12 distance (1.322(4) Å) within the six-membered chelate ring (formed by each of the anionic (HL)⁻ ligand) is much shorter than the N1-C1 single bond (1.437(4) Å) of the same molecule and it is in the range of typical imine (C=N) length (~1.35 Å)³⁻⁶. The N3-C12 distance (1.322(4) Å) within the six-membered chelate ring (formed by each of the anionic (HL)⁻ ligand) is much shorter than the N1-C1 single bond (1.437(4) Å) of the same molecule and it is in the range of typical imine (C=N) length (~1.35 Å) similar to Pd^{II} and Pt^{II}³⁻⁶. The N1-N2 distance (1.294(4) Å) is similar to coordinated azo (-N=N-) length of Pd and Pt complexes³⁻⁶. These azo and imine lengths enabled us to infer the formation of six-membered azoimine chelate like bivalent palladium and platinum^{3,5}. The distortion in the phenyl ring (C7, C8,...C12) adjacent to the chelate ring with four longer (1.41 Å) and two shorter (1.33 Å) C-C distances also supported the imine formation due to delocalization of negative charge of the deprotonated anionic ligands.

Electronic structure of (HL)₂M complexes :

EHMO calculation were performed on (HL)₂M complexes^{26,27}. The crystallographic coordinates of (HL)₂M (M = Ni, Pd, Pt) were used as the geometrical parameters. FMO analyses were carried out to obtain the in-

teraction and energy level diagram. Partial energy level and interaction diagram has been shown in Figs. S7-S12 (supplementary material) it is important to know the composition of four frontiers orbital HOMO-1, HOMO, LUMO and LUMO+1. The contributions of specific atoms or group of atoms are given in Table 2. The composition of HOMO shows a metal-ligand mixed orbital for all the three complexes while LUMO and LUMO+1 are ligand orbitals. The π* combination of azo nitrogens contribute the most in LUMO and LUMO+1. For (HL)¹₂Ni and (HL)¹₂Pt, this is ligand orbital but for (HL)¹₂Pd contribution of metal orbital is 67%. The relative HOMO-LUMO energy gaps in (HL)¹₂Ni, (HL)¹₂Pd and (HL)¹₂Pt is consistent with the relative energies of the low energy absorption i.e.

Let us consider the Δ_E is the E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO}.

$$\Delta_E = E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO}$$

$$\Delta_E^{Ni} = 0.8089 \text{ eV}, \Delta_E^{Pd} = 0.7912 \text{ eV},$$

$$\Delta_E^{Pt} = 0.828 \text{ eV}$$

If, E_{tr} ≡ Δ_E^{Ni}, then it is consistent with the results obtained from EHMO calculations.

Now it is interesting to analyse the electron transfer properties of (HL)₂M. (HL)¹₂Ni and (HL)¹₂Pt display several serial redox response. Four irreversible reductive responses were attributed to ligand centered reductions on LUMO and LUMO+1. Both these orbitals are ligand based orbitals as obtained from EHMO calculations. The first two oxidations are from the M-L mixed HOMO while the other two from ligand centered HOMO-1 of (HL)¹₂Ni and (HL)¹₂Pt.

Table 2. EHMO, λ_{max} and redox data

Compd.	MO	Energy	% of orbital contribution				λ _{max} (nm)	Cyclic voltammetric data (V)
			-N=N-	-CH=N	Other carbon	Metal		
Ni(HL) ₂	HOMO	-11.3244	12	25	20	23	651	-1.5, -1.3, -0.98, -0.80, 0.58, 0.85, 1.15, 1.61
	LUMO	-10.5155	57	11	12	0		
Pd(HL) ₂	HOMO	-11.3863	4	14	8	50	628	-1.72, -1.39, -1.2, 0.91, 1.21, 1.55, 1.66
	LUMO	-10.5951	58	12	12	0		
Pt(HL) ₂	HOMO	-11.3609	8	20	20	31	756	-1.5, -1.2, -0.98, 0.60 0.81
	LUMO	-10.5329	56	10	16	0		

Redox studies :

The redox properties of the ligands and complexes in acetonitrile solution was examined under dinitrogen environment cyclic voltammetrically at a Pt-disk working electrode using tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (NBu_4ClO_4) as a supporting electrolyte and the potentials are reported with reference to the SCE. The results were collected and are given in Table 2. In case of ligands no redox responses were observed. The several ligand oxidation and reduction couple was observed with respect to SCE. For $(\text{HL}^1)_2\text{Ni}$ four consecutive oxidation and reduction waves are observed positive and negative side to SCE but in case of $(\text{HL}^1)_2\text{Pd}$ and $(\text{HL}^1)_2\text{Pt}$ three negative response, four and two positive response observed. These potential may be due to successive reduction and oxidation of azo functions in the ligand frame^{11,12} analogous to azo pyridine and azopyrimidine system.

Materials :

All starting materials were used as received from commercial sources; the solvents were purchased from E. Merck, Kolkata, India, and purified and dried by reported procedure³. *o*-Phenylenediamine, nitrobenzene, 4-nitrotoluene were purchased from Loba, Kolkata, India. Nickel acetate, potassium carbonate were purchased from E. Merck, Kolkata, India. The ligand 2-(phenylazo)aniline and 2-(*p*-tolylazo)aniline were prepared following the reported procedure³⁻⁵

Physical measurements :

Microanalysis (C, H, N) was performed using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer L120-00A FT-IR spectrometer with the samples prepared with KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-2401 PC spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were obtained on Bruker 300 NMR spectrometers in CDCl_3 using TMS as the internal standard. Electrochemical measurements were made under dinitrogen atmosphere using a PAR model VERSASTAT-II potentiostat. A platinum disc working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and an aqueous saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) were used in a three-electrode configuration. Elec-

trochemical data was collected at 298 K and is uncorrected for junction potentials.

Syntheses of complexes :

$(\text{HL}^1)_2\text{Ni}$: 2-(Arylazo)aniline H_2L^1 (126 mg, 0.76 mmol) was dissolved in methanol (40 mL), and to it $\text{Ni}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (100 mg, 0.38 mmol) was added. The mixture was then heated to reflux in presence of K_2CO_3 for 1 h. A green solid was precipitated. The solid green mass filtered and washed with petroleum ether. 20 mL of dichloromethane was poured into the solid mass and filtered again. Slow evaporation of this green dichloromethane solution furnished the pure crystals of $(\text{HL}^1)_2\text{Ni}$. Yield : 80% (Found : C, 63.80; H, 4.45; N, 18.65. Calcd for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{Ni}$ (mol. wt. 451.15) : C, 63.83; H, 4.43; N, 18.61%); IR (KBr) : ν 3322 (N-H), 1339 (N=N), 1610 (C=N) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 5.89 (1H, s, NH), 6.84–6.75 (2H, m), 7.19–7.21 (1H, d), 7.39–7.41 (1H, d), 7.49 (2H, t), 7.83 (3H, d). Electronic spectral data in dichloromethane solution : (λ , nm, (ϵ , M^{-1} , cm^{-1})) : 651 (6795), 400 (23436), 282 (86013), 233 (58209).

$(\text{HL}^2)_2\text{Ni}$: The compound $(\text{HL}^2)_2\text{Ni}$ was prepared following the same procedure as described in the case of $(\text{HL}^1)_2\text{Ni}$ using H_2L^2 in place of H_2L^1 . Yield : 75% (Found : C, 65.21; H, 4.98; N, 17.59. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{Ni}$ (mol. wt. 479.18) : C, 65.16; H, 5.04; N, 17.53%); IR (KBr) : ν 3324 (N-H), 1342 (N=N), 1610 (C=N) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 5.82 (1H, s, NH), 6.04 (1H, d), 6.36 (1H, t), 6.78 (1H, t), 7.19 (2H, d), 7.29 (1H, t), 7.80 (2H, d). Electronic spectral data in dichloromethane solution : (λ , nm, (ϵ , M^{-1} , cm^{-1})) : 654 (31500), 400 (41150), 282 (14500), 233 (2300).

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystals of $(\text{HL}^1)_2\text{Ni}$ was obtained by slow evaporation of dichloromethane solution. Data were collected on a Bruker SMART CCD diffractometer using Mo-K α monochromator ($\lambda = 0.71043$). Structure solutions were performed using Shelx 97 PC version program. The full matrix least square and anisotropic refinements were performed on all the atoms. Hydrogen atoms were included at calculated positions. The data collection parameters and relevant crystal data are collected in Table 3.

Table 3. Crystal data and structure refinement details for compound (HL¹)₂Ni

Formula	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₆ Ni
Mol. wt.	451.15
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	P21/c
<i>a</i> (Å)	6.148(13)
<i>b</i> (Å)	15.23(3)
<i>c</i> (Å)	11.10(2)
β (deg)	95.54(5)
λ (Mo Kα) (mm)	0.71073
<i>V</i> (Å) ³	2038(3)
<i>Z</i>	2
Temperature (K)	298
<i>D</i> calcd. (g cm ⁻³)	1.449
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.962
<i>R</i> (all data)	0.0370
<i>wR</i> ₂ [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	0.0861
<i>R</i> 1/ <i>Gof</i>	1.04

Supplementary data :

Figs. S1-S6 are supplied as supplementary materials of UV-Vis, IR, ¹H NMR spectra of (HL)₂Ni. Figs. S7-S12 are supplied as MO results for (HL¹)₂Ni, (HL¹)₂Pd and (HL¹)₂Pt. Crystallographic data of (HL¹)₂Ni for the structural analysis have been deposited with The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC Reference Number 637569 (in CIF format). Copies of this information may be obtained free from the Director, CCDC, 12, Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EW, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336-033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

Acknowledgement

My special thank to Dr. Surajit Chattopadhyay, University of Kalyani, for his valuable suggestions throughout this work. Professor J. H. Huang, National Changhua University of Education, Taiwan thank for X-ray structure determination. The necessary laboratory and infrastructural facility are provided by the Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani.

References

1. J. Pratihar, N. Maiti and S. Chattopadhyay, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 6111.
2. J. Pratihar, N. Maiti, P. Pattanayak and S. Chattopadhyay, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 1953.
3. N. Maiti, S. Pal and S. Chattopadhyay, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, **40**, 2204 and references therein.
4. N. Maiti, B. K. Dirghangi and S. Chattopadhyay, *Polyhedron*, 2003, **22**, 3109.
5. N. Maiti and S. Chattopadhyay, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 2327.
6. D. Patra, J. L. Pratihar, B. Shee, P. Pattanayak and S. Chattopadhyay, *Polyhedron*, 2006, **25**, 2637.
7. J. Pratihar, D. Patra and S. Chattopadhyay, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2005, **690**, 4816.
8. N. Kano, M. Yamamura and T. Kawashima, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 6250.
9. M. Yamamura, N. Kano and T. Kawashima, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 11954.
10. J. Yoshino, N. Kano and T. Kawashima, *Chem. Commun.*, 2007, 559.
11. P. K. Santra, D. Das, T. K. Misra, R. Roy, C. Sinha and S.-M. Peng, *Polyhedron*, 1999, **18**, 1909.
12. T. K. Misra, D. Das, C. Sinha, P. Ghosh and C. K. Pal, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 1672.
13. K. K. Sarker, B. G. Chand, K. Suwa, J. Cheng, T.-H. Lu, J. Otsuki and C. Sinha, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 670.
14. P. Gupta, S. Dutta, F. Basuli, S.-M. Peng, G.-H. Lee and S. Bhattacharya, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 460.
15. S. Nag, P. Gupta, R. J. Butcher and S. Bhattacharya, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 4814.
16. P. Gupta, R. J. Butcher and S. Bhattacharya, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2003, **42**, 5405.
17. R. Aharyya, F. Basuli, R. Z. Wang, T. C. Mak and S. Bhattacharya, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 704.
18. A. H. Velders, K. van der Schilden, A. C. G. Hotze, J. Reedijk, H. Kooijman and A. L. Spek, *Dalton Trans.*, 2004, 448.
19. C. Das, A. Saha, C. H. Hung, G.-H. Lee, S.-M. Peng and S. Goswami, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2003, **42**, 198.
20. S. Ghumaan, S. Mukherjee, S. Kar, D. Roy, S. M. Mobin, R. B. Sunoj and G. K. Lahiri, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, 4426.
21. K. K. Kamar, S. Das, C.-H. Hung, A. Castineiras, M. D. Kuzmin, C. Rillo, J. Bartolome and S. Goswami, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2003, **42**, 5367.

22. C. Das, S.-M. Peng, G.-H. Lee and S. Goswami, *New J. Chem.*, 2002, **26**, 222.
23. T. Yitaka, M. Kurihara, K. Kubo and H. Nishihara, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2000, **39**, 3438.
24. M. Kurihara and H. Nishihara, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **226**, 125 and references therein.
25. A. D. Garnovskii, A. I. Uraev and V. I. Minkin, *Arkivoc*, 2004, (iii), 29.
26. C. Mealli and D. M. Proserpio, *CACAO Version 4.0*. Italy, 1994.
27. C. Mealli and D. M. Proserpio, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1990, **67**, 399.